

Fig. 5

Figure 5. Comparison of the cloud field in optical and far-infrared versus CO emission. Left: DSS2 red optical image (inverted greyscale) showing the cloud in dust extinction. Centre: IRAS-IRIS far-infrared composite showing thermal dust emission at the same position. Right: Dame & Thaddeus (2022) all-sky CO survey at the cloud coordinates. CO emission is detected in parts of the surrounding field but is absent at the cloud position, confirming a genuine non-detection rather than a coverage gap. All panels are centred on RA 19h 47m 30s, Dec $-02^{\circ} 27' 07''$ (J2000) and cover the same field of view.